

THE ROLE OF MAHALLAS AND GUZARS IN TIMURID SAMARKAND'S URBAN INFRASTRUCTURE

Sidikova Mastura Khakberdievna

PhD, Associate Professor, “Silk Road” International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20274111>

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Samarqandning qadimiy mahallalari, xususan, Temuriylar davrida shahar infratuzilmasining organik asosini tashkil etgan muhim bo‘g‘in sifatidagi ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. Samarqandning tarixiy shaharsozligida, xususan Temuriylar davrida mahallalar, guzarlar shahar infratuzilmasining organik asosini tashkil etgan bo‘lib, o‘rta asr manbalarida Tagachiyon, Naqqoshon, Suzangaron va Puli Gotifar kabi ko‘chalar, shuningdek, Dari Zanjir, Mirzo Polodi, Qozikalon, Kok Mashit, Qoshkhovuz, Khoja Zulmurod, Makhdumi Xorazmiy, Madrasa Safed, Khoja Nisbatdor, Hovuzi Sangin, Gur Amir va Oqsaroy kabi mahallalar tilga olinadi. Uylarning eshigi ko‘chaga qaragan. Ichki ayvonlar va chordoqlar hovliga qaragan holda, oilaviy hayot mustahkam birliklar ichida rivojlangan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Mahalla, guzar, Samarqand, temuriylar, qal‘a, darvozalar, me‘morchilik

Abstract: This article is devoted to an analysis of the ancient neighborhoods of Samarkand, particularly their importance as an important link that formed the organic basis of the city's infrastructure during the Timurid era. In Samarkand's historical urban development, particularly during the Timurid era, neighborhoods (mahallalar) and passages (guzars) formed the organic backbone of the city's infrastructure. Medieval sources mention streets like Tagachiyon, Naqqoshon, Suzangaron, and Puli Gotifar, as well as neighborhoods such as Dari Zanjir, Mirzo Polodi, Qozikalon, Kok Mashit, Qoshkhovuz, Khoja Zulmurod, Makhdumi Xorazmiy, Madrasa Safed, Khoja Nisbatdor, Hovuzi Sangin, Gur Amir, and Oqsaroy. Houses had doors facing the street, while inner verandas and attics overlooked courtyards, fostering family life within strong communal units.

Keywords: Mahalla, guzar, Samarkand, Timurids, Citadel, gates, architecture

Резюме: Статья посвящена анализу древних кварталов Самарканда, в частности, их важности как звена, сформировавшего органическую основу городской инфраструктуры в эпоху Тимуридов. В историческом градостроительстве Самарканда, особенно в тимуридскую эпоху, махалли (mahallalar) и гузара (guzars) составляли органический каркас городской инфраструктуры. Средневековые источники упоминают улицы вроде Тагачиён, Наққошон, Сузангарон и Пули Готифар, а также махалли, такие как Дари Занжир, Мирзо Полоди, Қозикалон, Кок Мечет, Қошхувуз, Ходжа Зулмурод, Махдуми Хорезмий, Мадрасаи Сафед, Ходжа Нисбатдор, Хаузӣ Сангин, Гур Эмир и Оқсарой. Двери домов выходили на улицу, а внутренние айваны и чердаки смотрели во дворы, способствуя семейной жизни в крепких общинных ячейках.

Ключевые слова: Махалля, гузар, Самарканд, Темуриды, Цитадель, ворота, архитектура

It is known that Samarkand, located in the central part of Central Asia in a strategically important region where major trade and cultural routes intersect, has played a significant role as an ancient city. Its geographical position holds particular importance on the Great Silk Road.

Over centuries, it has become one of the main centers connecting East and West. Thus, Samarkand has not only served as a hub for trade but also played a major role as a great center for science, craftsmanship, and cultural exchange.

From ancient times, this region has been a cradle of human civilization, with archaeological and historical data indicating that life formed very early in Samarkand and its surroundings. Due to its favorable natural-geographical conditions, water sources, and fertile lands, the city became one of the major human settlements even in ancient times. Throughout history, Samarkand has also been renowned as the capital of great empires. During the reigns of various dynasties and states, it fulfilled the functions of a political, economic, and cultural center. Especially during the Timurid era, Samarkand rose to a high level of development, becoming one of the most prosperous and prestigious cities in the East. As a result of urban beautification, the construction of new residential areas, mosques, madrasas, bazaars, and gardens under Amir Timur and the Timurids, neighborhoods expanded, and their social and territorial significance further increased. During this period, Samarkand transformed not only into the state capital but also into a major political, cultural, and economic center.

It should be particularly emphasized that in Central Asian urban planning, quarters-passages or neighborhoods played a crucial role as the basic unit of the city. This is because neighborhoods were not only administrative-territorial divisions but also communities of relatives and people who knew each other closely, standing together in both hard and good times.

"If we focus briefly on the etymology of the terms 'Guzar' or 'Mahalla'. The term 'Guzar' means 'passage' or 'passing place' in the Tajik language, and in some sources, it is described as the main street connecting the mahalla center or city center." (Manoev 2024: 235) "The word 'Mahalla' means 'city within a city' in Arabic. In fact, the word 'Mahalla' began to be used after the Arabs entered Central Asia. In the early Middle Ages, the first community organizations in the form of mahallas, villages, and towns were called 'Naf.'" (Gulyamova 2025: 213) "Possibly, the word 'Naf' means 'center' and is compared to the word 'Kindik-Nof,' the center of the human body."

"The oldest example of urban planning in the history of Samarkand city is considered to be the Afrosiyob city-fortress. It is located on the northern outskirts of present-day Samarkand, with an area of 219 hectares, surrounded by a wall approximately 5.5 km long. To the east of Afrosiyob flow the Obimashhad, and to the north, the Obirahmat and Siyob rivers. Inside the city, there were various artisan mahallas, streets, places of worship, markets, guzars, and irrigation networks. In the northern part of the city, on an area of 19 hectares, there rose the extremely fortified ruler's residence – 'Kohandiz-ark.'" (Muhammadjonov 2015:) "Additionally, along the perimeter of the city, a clay wall 7-8 meters thick and a defensive wall 12 meters thick were erected. The Afrosiyob defensive wall was majestic in thickness, like the defensive walls of Panjikent and Paykend. For example, the three-ring defensive wall reached a thickness of 10 meters in some places. In general, the preserved height of this defensive wall reaching 13.5 meters confirms that it was truly a powerful fortification in its time. The city had four gates: northern, southern, eastern, and western gates. In historical sources and literature, these gates are mentioned under the names Bukhara, Kesh, China, and Navbahor gates." (Kubaev 2016: 12)

"Samarkand was the capital of the Sogdiana state from the 4th century BC until the 6th century AD. During this period, trade relations between Eastern and Western states intensified further through the Great Silk Road, and in this process, Samarkand city occupied an important place as a trade center and transit city. The city was located at the crossroads of the Great Silk Road routes running from south to north and from west to east.

The Arab historian and traveler Ibn Haikal, who lived in the 9th-10th centuries, left valuable information about the Sogd region. (Berdimurodov 2015: 95) Additionally, in the works of the Arab historian al-Asakir 'History of the City of Damascus', and the Arab geographer Ibn Hawqal's 'Book of the Depiction of the Earth, (Mamadaliyev 2017: 54) precise information is provided about Samarkand city, including its canals, dams, villages, and cities in the Samarkand province. According to Ibn Hawqal, Samarkand city had a citadel and four gates – China, Navbahor, Bukhara, and Kat gates. In the 9th-10th centuries, due to political stability in Movarounnahr, trade and crafts developed in the Samarkand oasis, and large-scale construction and architectural works were carried out. As a result of archaeological excavations conducted in 1919 in the ancient mahalla of Samarkand – Asfiza, remnants of the palace of a Samanid ruler were discovered in this area. (Pugachenkova/Rempel 1958: 96)

“During the Qarakhanid period, production and external economic relations developed further in Samarkand. The city became one of the centers of handicrafts and culture. According to their occupations, craftsmen lived in special mahallas such as coppersmiths, needle-makers, potters, tailors, and others. ¹The analysis of historical studies shows that the origin of the division of Samarkand’s population into mahallas according to occupation in the 18th century actually goes back to the Samanid period and especially to the Qarakhanid period. This is because trade and craftsmanship developed in Samarkand first under the Samanids and then under the Qarakhanids, and the city’s population lived very densely.

Information about the life and appearance of the city in the 11th to early 13th centuries has been almost entirely lost. Based on archaeological sources, it can be said that the potters’ mahalla, which emerged in the city area in the 10th century, expanded toward the west and southwest. Samarkand’s namazgah was located outside the city, extending westward from Afrosiyob and built on the site of an old Buddhist temple. One of Samarkand’s city gates was therefore called the Navbahor Gate.” (Mamadaliyev 2016: 32)

“In a work by al-Nasafi written before the Mongol invasion, the city of Samarkand is said to have had 12 cemeteries, 3 palaces, 15 mosques, 4 *balda*,² and the names of 3 districts. (Mamadaliyev 2016: 36) In 1220, Samarkand was captured by the troops of Genghis Khan, and an unprecedented plundering began in history. Samarkand was destroyed to an extraordinary extent by the Mongol invaders. The Arab historian Ibn al-Athir, who witnessed this aggression, described these events clearly and vividly in his memoirs. (Grekov/Yakubovskiy 1956: 46)

The Mongols’ attack on Samarkand is reflected today in the appearance of the Afrosiyob hill. After the Mongol invasion, Samarkand remained one of the important centers of the Chagatai Ulus until the 1340s. In 1370, Samarkand became the capital of Amir Temur’s state. The great commander paid very close attention to the city’s prosperity. On his order, a new city was built on a natural hill south of Afrosiyob in 1371–1372. The construction work involved the most experienced builders of the time, and it was led by Amir Oqbuqa. (Boytullaev 2007: 605) According to A. Malikov, Timur’s construction and urban development work in Samarkand can be divided into two periods: the first, from 1370 to 1385, during which Timur’s fortress, defensive walls, the Rhubod, the mausoleums of Shaykh Nuriddin Basir, the Shah-i-Zinda complex, as well as some gardens and palace complexes were built. The second period covered 1386 to 1405, when major buildings in Samarkand were constructed. These works employed

¹ It is not unlikely that the present-day “So‘zangaron” (Needle-makers) mahalla of Samarkand emerged during the Qarakhanid period. – R. Hodizoda. *Samarqandnoma*. T., 2011, p. 33.

² The word “balda” meant “small town.”

skilled artisans brought from Timur's military campaigns in Iran, Khwarazm, the Golden Horde, the Ottoman Empire, Syria, and India. (Malikov 2022) "The city was encircled by a strong and high defensive wall. The wall was 8 meters high and more than 3 meters thick at the base, and its outer perimeter was reinforced with a wide and deep moat. This place was called Hisor, and an Ark was built on the natural hill in its western part. The area where the Ark stood covered more than 34 hectares. The Ark contained government offices, mosques and madrasas, royal residences, a huge library holding 15,000 volumes of rare books, Amir Temur's treasury and throne, a mint, weapons workshops, a bathhouse, a pool, a prison, and other buildings." (Boytullaev 2010: 30)

The fortress was not just a fortification of Amir Temur, but first of all a fortified administrative and military center of the capital. There were six gates along the city walls: in the north - Akhanin and Shaikhzoda, in the west - Chorsu, in the south - Korizgoh (later Namozgoh, then called Khoja Ahror) and Suzangaron, in the east - Feruza. Streets leading to the neighborhoods were formed from these gates entering the city. Each neighborhood had its own mosque, pond, market, butcher's shop, bakery, madrasa and, of course, the neighborhood's Aksaqoli - "Kalontarin". The drainage system was well established on the streets of the neighborhood, and water flowed from ditches along the streets.

The names of some streets and neighborhoods during the Timurid era can be found in foundation documents and historical works. In particular, street names such as Tagachiyon, Naqqoshon, Suzangaron, Puli Gotifar, and neighborhoods such as Dari Zanjir, Mirzo Polodi, Qozikalon, Kok mashit, Qoshkhovuz, Khoja Zulmurod, Makhdumi Khorezmiy, Madrasa Safed, Khoja Nisbatdor, Hauzi Sangin, Gur emir, Oqsaroy, Zingaron are mentioned in historical sources. (Abramov 1989: 6) In particular, the name of the Dari Zanjir neighborhood is also associated with the name of the city gate. The name of this neighborhood is also mentioned under the name Hayati Khan (Khan's Palace). Suyurgatmish,³ a descendant of Genghis Khan, lived in this neighborhood. (Malikov 2022)

One of the greatest achievements of architectural urban planning thought and practice during the Timurid era was architectural complexes. City neighborhoods consisted of winding streets and high walls, and family life took place inside. Only the doors of the houses opened to the street, the windows were verandas, and all the attics looked out onto the inner courtyard. In the city center and main streets, magnificent architecturally magnificent buildings were built. The residential unit of the city was the neighborhood, which was united into a number of districts. The neighborhoods were not formed on the basis of a city building plan. Perhaps over the centuries they were formed depending on the social class, the type of production, and the aspect of community life. Due to this spontaneous structure, narrow streets appeared, forming a tangled network. However, in sharp contrast to them, the formation of the main architectural complexes in the city in the form of a complex of magnificent buildings was one of the highest achievements of the era of Timur and the Timurids.

The city had large bazaars such as Kappon, Muhammad Sultan, Muhammad Qasim and others. In addition, beautiful and luxurious baths such as Mirzoyi (built by Mirzo Ulugbek), Qasim Sultan, Muhammad Qasim baths, Kabut Mosque, Muqatta Mosque, Lyak Lyaka Mosque, Attori Mosques, Jauzani, Amir Burunduk, Amir Firuzshah, Amir Shohmalik, Shah Khoja Ahrar, Shahzoda Abdulla madrasas, Tuman Aga and Sheikh Abulais khanaqas were built in the most

³ It is known that Amir Temur could not ascend the throne of Samarkand as a khan because he was not a descendant of Genghis Khan, and therefore he ascended as Suyurgatmish Khan, a descendant of Genghis Khan.

densely populated areas of Samarkand. Unfortunately, for some reason, most of these buildings have not survived to our days. (Pugachenkova/Rempel 1958:100)

The Spanish ambassador Rui Gonzalez de Clavijo, who was at Timur's palace, spoke about the infrastructure of the city of Samarkand at that time, recording in his diary information about its wealth, streets, markets, squares, the lifestyle of the palace dwellers, and other details. The Spanish ambassador expressed his amazement at the construction and development work carried out in the city of Samarkand. The city was densely planted with ornamental and fruit trees, resembling a dense forest when viewed from the Cho'pon Ota hill.

Among the buildings built in Timur's Ark, the Kuksaroy and Bostansaroy buildings were very luxurious. Kuksaroy was a four-story tall building that served as the government palace, that is, the divan. The Bostansaroy building was a retreat inside the fortress. Historians suggest that the Bostansarai building may have been named so because it was located in an orchard.

In conclusion, it can be said that Samarkand has been the center of human civilization since ancient times. However, as a result of centuries of conquests, most of them have not survived to this day. The city's infrastructure, street names, and the topography of neighborhoods have changed and developed along with the changes in political, economic, and social life of a certain period. Especially during the Timurid period, the infrastructure of Samarkand neighborhoods developed and expanded in accordance with the city plan. Each neighborhood center was formed in accordance with the requirements of daily life. Interestingly, most neighborhoods that emerged during the Timurid period, despite centuries of political and social changes, have retained their historical toponymic names among the local population today. This, in turn, embodies the living history of the city. Also, in order to develop the tourism sector in Samarkand, it is important to preserve the toponymic names of historical neighborhoods and conduct more extensive scientific research on the historical neighborhoods of the city.

References

1. Muhammadjonov, A. (2015). *Tarix falsafasi – ma'naviyat ko'zgusi*. [Publisher not specified], Toshkent.
2. Mamadaliev, H. (2017). *Ўzbekiston shaharlari IX-XII asrlarda*. Adabiyot uchqunlari, Toshkent.
3. Mamadaliev, H. (2016). *IX-XV asrlarda O'rta Osiyo shaharlari*. [Publisher not specified], Toshkent.
4. Berdimurodov, A. (2015). *Samarkand tarixidan tomchilar*. [Publisher not specified], Toshkent.
5. Boytullaev, R., & Ostonova, G. (2010). *Mozay daf taridan sahifalar*. [Publisher not specified], Toshkent.
6. Abramov, M. (1989). *Guzari Samarkanda*. Uzbekiston, Toshkent.
7. Malikov, A. (2022). The cultural traditions of urban planning in Samarkand during the epoch of Timur. In C. Baumer, M. Novák, & S. Rutishauser (Eds.), *Cultures in contact: Central Asia as focus of trade, cultural exchange and knowledge transmission* (pp. 407-xxx). SVA Series. Harrassowitz Verlag. <https://doi.org/10.13173/9783447118804.407>
8. Gulyamova, A. N. (2025). History of mahallas of Uzbekistan and their evolution during the historical period. *Web of Humanities: Journal of Social Science and Humanitarian Research*, 3(5), 213-216. <https://webofjournals.com/index.php/9/article/view/4503>
9. Mannoyev, S. (2024, May 16-18). *Formation and development of neighborhood (mahalla) in Uzbekistan* [Conference paper]. International Scientific and Practical Conference *Cultural*

Echoes on the Silk Road: Bridging Historical Legacies with Modern Tourism.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11218665>

10. Kubaev, S. Sh. (2016). Ilk o'rta asr so'gd mudofaa tizimining rivojlanishining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari. *O'zbekiston arxeologiyasi*, (1), 12.
11. Grekov, B. D., & Yakubovskiy, Yu. A. (1956). *Oltin O'rda va uning qulashi*. Toshkent.
12. Hodizoda, R. (2011). *Samarqandnoma*. [Publisher not specified], Toshkent.
13. Boytullaev, R. (2007, January 20). Samarqand Arki [Newspaper article]. *Qadriyat*, (3), 605.
14. Pugachenkova, & Rempel, L. I. (1958). *Vidayushchiesya pamyatniki arkhitekturi Uzbekistana*.